

USE OF MODERN TECHNICAL TOOLS IN SCHOOL HISTORY CLASSES

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Annotation: *This article describes the technical means of education, their role in improving the efficiency of the educational process, the importance of effective and efficient use of technical means, based on various theoretical and practical analyzes.*

Keywords: *technical means of education, technical means, auxiliary technical means, graphoprojector, text means, image means, model means, real means.*

INTRODUCTION Uzbekistan is going through the most responsible stage of national development - a period of sharp changes in social, political and economic life. At the end of the twentieth century, at the beginning of the XXI century, every citizen of our society faces the problem of summarizing the years left behind and defining a plan for various aspects of future life, which imposes a great task on social scientists. The above applies to the field of education, which determines the success of all aspects of public life, as well as the foundation of the scholar.

The system of personnel training in our country has a high general and professional culture, creative, social activism, the ability to find the right path in political and social life, the formation of a new generation of personnel capable of promoting and solving future tasks, it also promotes the pedagogical idea of educating citizens who are well-rounded, well-adapted to life in society, consciously mastering educational and professional programs, and feel responsible to society, the state and the family.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

As provided by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" dated September 23, 2020, provides the necessary amount of professional knowledge, skills and abilities for the implementation of training activities. Training provides deepening and updating of professional knowledge, skills and abilities, serves to increase the category, level, rank and position of personnel.

Production is reflected in the national model of training as "the main customer, which determines the demand for personnel, as well as the requirements for the quality and level of their training, a participant in the process of financial and logistical support of the training system."

DISCUSSION

Today, the formation of new social relations in our society, the integration of education into the world education system, the development of democratization and development processes require a new approach to modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process. The need for the introduction and mastery of modern pedagogical technologies in the training of personnel has been repeatedly stated, and the need to bring them to educational institutions. For many years, pedagogical technologies have been viewed as the implementation of the learning process using technical means. Only from the 70s of the XX century in the pedagogical literature began to reinterpret this concept as a means of education.

Teaching aids- Demonstration of educational material, as well as auxiliary materials that increase the effectiveness of teaching. Educational tools are divided into:

1. Technical means of teaching
2. Auxiliary technical means
3. Teaching materials

Technical means of education- Facilitates the visual presentation of educational material, its systematic delivery, allows students to understand and better remember the educational material (slide projector, graphoprojector, board-notebook, board-stand, flipchart, video films).

Auxiliary training tools- graphs, drawings, models, etc. (models, diagrams, schemes, maps, etc.).

Teaching materials- training materials, exercises to strengthen the mastered training materials. These help to activate students 'independent work (worksheet, note, checklist, texts).

When using teaching aids, it is important for the teacher, the student, and the individual to choose the right options for the lesson to be effective. Tools for teachers: manuals on teaching methods of the subject, personal methodology, methodological recommendations on complex issues, methodological developments prepared by teachers, logical structures are important. Student textbook, textbook or teacher's lecture texts, tables, various maps, task cards, etc., posters, diagrams, models, models, standards, demonstrations for the lesson equipment for laboratory practical work, audiovisual aids, filmstrips, videos, slides are all part of the technical means of education. The chosen method, form and means must complement each other. In order to use the teaching tools listed above effectively, it is important for the teacher to determine which tool to use when based on the purpose and content of the lesson.

There are six types of teaching aids:

1. Text tools.
2. Visual aids.
3. Audio visual aids.
4. Auxiliary (equipment) means.

5. Model tools.

6. Real tools.

Text tools- For teachers and students: manuals on teaching methods of the subject, personal methodology, methodological developments prepared by teachers, logical structures, science textbooks, historical and artistic, depending on the topic literature, text of lectures on science.

Visual aids- Facilitates the demonstration of educational material, its systematic delivery; allows students to understand and remember the learning material (video projector, videos, pictures, sculptures, portraits).

Audio visual aids- Vote on the text, language tools, use of radio broadcasts, transcripts, various discs, etc.

Auxiliary equipment- overhead projector, whiteboard, whiteboard, flipchart, etc.).

Model tools- graphs, drawings, diagrams, maps.

Real tools- Museum exhibits, models and mock-ups, archeological materials, historical objects, etc. in history lessons.

RESULTS

Experience has shown that the use of the following technical tools in history education is effective:

- simple technical means: simple devices made of wood or other material for placing cards and training papers, a portable classroom board, a double-sided folding classroom board that hangs on the classroom wall, etc.

- audio devices: discs and plates for broadcasting on tape recorders, computers and other technical means. The use of these tools in history lessons is important in recording and delivering to the students the works of various scholars or extracurricular broadcasts of the lesson on television or radio, and so on.

Sound equipment also includes radio and audio broadcasts. The teacher can conduct the lesson in a more meaningful and interesting way with the students in the history lesson by means of radio or pre-recorded audio-related lessons. A tape recorder can also be used as a technical tool in history lessons. Radio and television broadcasts of educational and extracurricular activities, meeting materials with participants of historical events, labor heroes, writers, public figures can be reflected in these tape recordings. These lessons will not be repeated, but the recordings on the recorded tape can be used for many years and at any time in class and in extracurricular activities.

There are the following basic ways to use educational audio films in history teaching practice:

a) The teacher connects his statement with the most important and bright shots of the educational audio film. Explains the selected frames and draws appropriate conclusions.

b) Conducts a lesson with 10-15 minutes of short instructional audio films

- c) A special film lesson will be organized
- d) An audio film is shown outside of class.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that conducting history lessons with the help of modern and effective technical means will help students to master this science well and perfectly, to increase their interest in science.

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CORRECTLY ORGANIZING HISTORY LESSONS USING INTERESTING GAME METHODS

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Annotation: *In recent years, the basis of the ongoing reforms in the system of continuing education in our country is the dissemination of best practices that can meet international educational standards, as well as practical work to achieve high efficiency in the educational process with less physical effort.*

Keywords: *history, fun play, ground to theme, summary-tree crop*

The most important and urgent task facing general secondary school teachers today is to increase students' interest in learning and broaden their horizons. To date, a number of measures have been taken to implement this work, which has laid the foundation for the success of educational effectiveness in general secondary schools. One of the important conditions for the effectiveness of the lesson is that the teacher and the students search for the truth together and the students actively participate in the whole lesson process. Of course, practice shows that new pedagogical technologies are available to teachers.

Nowadays, every science teacher is tasked with a comprehensive view of man, his place and role in society. To do this, the teacher must master new forms, means and methods of education, and at the same time try to create modern pedagogical technologies, choose new traditional, effective methods of personal development and be creative.

The social sciences, including history, taught in schools play an important role in educating a person who embodies noble qualities. At school, students learn the basics of the history of human society, their struggle against foreign invaders, their struggle for freedom and happiness, for a bright future. At the same time, history lessons help the student to understand the current socio-political processes.

As we know, history is one of the most ancient sciences. The science of history can be called a "mirror" of the future, and based on this mirror, any person, society, nation can determine its own future. Today, it is not easy for Uzbekistan to become one of the developed countries. Therefore, in the process of teaching history, it is necessary to teach students to appreciate the present, not to repeat the mistakes of the past, to draw conclusions from the mistakes of the past. In addition, through the teaching of